

FAIR Workflows to establish IGSN for Samples in the Helmholtz Association

D6 – Registration of IGSNs for an exemplary subset of
Geo-Bio samples
(Hereon, GFZ, AWI)

Authors

Linda Baldewein (Hereon)

Tim Leefmann (Hereon)

Ulrike Kleeberg (Hereon)

Alexander Brauser (GFZ)

Kirsten Elger (GFZ)

Simone Frenzel (GFZ)

Birgit Heim (AWI)

Mareike Wieczorek (AWI)

Publication Date: March 31st, 2023

Contents

1. Introduction	3
1.1. Purpose of this document	3
1.2. Expedition database Hereon	3
2. IGSN registration	3
3. References	4
4. Appendix	5
4.1. List of acronyms	5

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of this document

This document contains deliverable D6 *Registration of IGSNs for an exemplary subset of Geo-Bio samples* of the project **FAIR Workflows** to establish IGSN for **S**amples in the **H**elmholtz Association (FAIR WISH) funded by the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration (HMC). Deliverable D6 is part of work package 6 *IGSN registration workflows for biogeochemical sample databases*.

This deliverable builds upon D2 *Exemplary standardised metadata templates for Geo-Bio Samples (vegetation, water, sediment, rock samples) for all uses cases* (Wieczorek et al., 2022), the FAIR WISH: Sample description template (Brauser et al., 2023) and D5 *Mapping of database metadata to machine readable IGSN metadata (Use Case Hereon)* (Baldewein et al., 2023) to register IGSNs for a subset of samples stored in the Hereon biogeochemical campaign database.

1.2. Expedition database Hereon

The expedition database at Hereon has been developed since 2016 within the coastMap project (Baldewein et al., 2018). Its aim is to allow querying and downloading of campaign data collected during ship and land-based sampling campaigns at the Hereon Institute of Carbon Cycles and Hereon Institute of Coastal Environmental Chemistry.

In D5 “*Mapping of database metadata to machine readable IGSN metadata (Use Case Hereon)*” (Baldewein et al., 2023), the mapping of the metadata within the database and the considerations of granularity and metadata quality of samples are described. The output of deliverable D5 is a comma-separated file containing the IGSN metadata of 12041 samples.

2. IGSN registration

In total, 12041 IGSNs for samples and stations of the Expedition database Hereon have been registered at GFZ Data Services (using Handle identifiers). The initial registration process is finished, but the metadata import is still ongoing. The IGSNs can be found in the GFZ Data Services catalogue at <https://dataservices.gfz-potsdam.de/igsn-new/> by filtering for the datacenter “Expedition database Hereon”. In the context of the IGSN DataCite partnership (Buys and Lehnert, 2021), all IGSNs are currently being re-registered as DataCite DOIs. Newly minted IGSNs will be also registered as DOIs.

3. References

Baldewein, L., Kleeberg, U., Lange, M., & Sauer, D. (2018). Coastal data portals to support marine science and management-the coastMap approach. *Bollettino di Geofisica*, 283.

Baldewein, Linda, Leefmann, Tim, Kleeberg, Ulrike, Brauser, Alexander, Elger, Kirsten, Frenzel, Simone, Heim, Birgit, & Wieczorek, Mareike. (2023). FAIR WISH D5 – Mapping of database metadata to machine readable IGSN metadata (Use Case Hereon). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7788654>

Brauser, Alexander, Wieczorek, Mareike, Frenzel, Simone, Heim, Birgit, Baldewein, Linda, Kleeberg, Ulrike, & Elger, Kirsten. (2023). FAIR WISH: Sample description template. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7520016>

Buys, M., & Lehnert, K. (2021). Partnership between IGSN and DataCite. DataCite. <https://doi.org/10.5438/7Z70-1155>

Wieczorek, Mareike, Heim, Birgit, Brauser, Alexander, Elger, Kirsten, & Baldewein, Linda. (2022). FAIR WISH D2 - Exemplary standardised metadata templates for Geo-Bio samples (vegetation, water, sediment, rock samples) for all use cases. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7147532>

4. Appendix

4.1. List of acronyms

AWI	Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research
FAIR	Guiding Principles for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable research data (Wilkinson et al., 2015, https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18)
FAIR WISH	FAIR Workflows to establish IGSN for Samples in the Helmholtz Association
GFZ	German Research Centre for Geosciences
IGSN	International Generic Sample Number